

Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

DMP

D1.2

Contact us

www.blurevproject.eu

info@blurevproject.eu

 @BlueRevEU

D1.2

DMP

DELIVERABLE TYPE

Report

MONTH AND DATE OF DELIVERY

Month 6, February 2023

WORK PACKAGE

1

LEADER

APRE

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

Public

AUTHOR(S)

Claudia Iasillo (APRE)

DOI / ISBN

10.5281/zenodo.7855345

Programme	Contract Number	Duration	Start
Horizon Europe	101060537	36 Months	September 2022

Contributors

Name	Organisation
Alessio Livio Spera	APRE
Anni Simonsen	FBCD
Alexandros Koukovinis	LOBA
Frode Krikedam	UiA
Daniel Bengtsson	RISE
Giovanna Ottaviani	NIBIO

Reviewers

Name	Organisation
Alessio Livio Spera	APRE

Revision History

Version	Date	Reviewer	Modifications
0.1	13/02/2023	Claudia Iasillo (APRE)	First draft
0.2	21/02/2023	Alessio Livio Spera (APRE), Anni Simonsen (FBCD), Alexandros Koukovinis (LOBA), Frode Krikedam (UiA), Daniel Bengtsson (RISE),	Comments from partners

		Giovanna Ottaviani (NIBIO)	
1.0	27/02/2023	Alessio Livio Spera (APRE)	Final version submitted
1.1	12/04/2023	Claudia Iasillo (APRE)	Updated version
1.2	21/04/2023	Alexandros Koukovinis (LOBA)	Comments from partners
2.0	24/04/2023	Claudia Iasillo, Alessio Livio Spera (APRE)	Final version submitted

The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf.

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
DFBG	Distretto della Pesca e Crescita Blu
DMP	Data Management Plan
EMU	Eesti Maaulikool
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Accessible
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
FBCD	Food Bio Cluster Denmark
GA4	Google Analytics 4
LOBA	GLOBAZ, S.A.
NIBIO	Norsk Institutt for Bioekonomi
RISE	Research Institutes of Sweden AB
UiA	Universitetet i Agder
WP	Work Package

Index of Contents

1	Executive Summary	9
2	Overview of the project	10
3	Research Data Management in BlueRev	11
3.1	Objectives of the DMP	11
3.2	The overall structure of the Data Management in BlueRev	11
3.3	Data management during BlueRev lifetime	12
3.4	Long term data management	12
4	Data collection	13
4.1	Data information	13
4.2	Organization of data collected	13
4.3	Data collected for each BlueRev Work Package	14
4.3.1	Work Package 1	14
4.3.2	Work Package 2	15
4.3.3	Work Package 3	16
4.3.4	Work Package 4	18
4.3.5	Work Package 5	19
4.3.6	Work Package 6	21
5	Data storage and backup	23
6	Data documentation	24
7	Data access	26
8	Data sharing and reuse	27
9	Data preservation and archiving	28
10	Privacy of participants	29
	Appendix 1 – Informed consent for events participation	32
	Appendix 2 – Informed consent for interviews and surveys	34
	Appendix 3 – Website Privacy Policy	36
	Appendix 4 – Website Cookies Policy	41

Index of Tables

Table 6-1 - Metadata included in the readme file of BlueRev data	24
Table 6-2 - Examples of files identification	25

Index of Figures

Figure 1 - BlueRev Concept.....	10
---------------------------------	----

1 Executive Summary

The current document, titled BlueRev DMP has been developed within the framework of the BlueRev project which is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101060537.

This deliverable describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the BlueRev project. As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR), the Data Management Plan (DMP) provides a summary of the main elements to take into account in the definition of the BlueRev data management policy to be used by project partners throughout the project activities. The DMP will provide indications about the management of all the data generated during the project activities, including how data will be collected, managed, stored and made available during the project and how they will be shared upon BlueRev completion.

The DMP is a living document that will be updated during the project lifetime according to the project's progresses and rising needs. A second version of BlueRev DMP will be provided at February 2024 (M18) and not only will describe the procedures applied, but it will provide more details about the long-term management and preservation of project data.

2 Overview of the project

BlueRev project focuses on the revitalisation of European local communities through innovative bio-based business models, governance frameworks and social innovations in the blue bio-based sector, to underline the benefits the wide deployment of the bio-based sector can offer.

To achieve its main objective, BlueRev project will identify and define a range of systems in the blue bio-based sector in 3 different pilot regions throughout Europe (i.e. Denmark, Italy and Estonia) to tailor value chains, from valorisation of co-products as feedstock to processing/conversion to final products, in order to revitalise local communities, both in a territorial and social sense and contribute to positive environmental and social impacts.

The project will first analyse these value chains according to social, economic and environmental barriers and potentialities, business models, local capacities (e.g. feedstocks, infrastructure, human skills, etc.) and innovation actors, including community knowledge and marginalised groups, by using existing or defining improved monitoring system and indicators to evaluate the effectiveness of the value chains. The project will also analyse the existing governance framework and how it can be improved.

The analysis will serve BlueRev to develop or replicate new governance and business models allowing the transition towards socially and environmentally responsible behaviour within all ranges (e.g. regulatory measures, corporate responsibility initiatives, education), to enable sufficient impacts and performances of the specific value chains and to allow replication across Europe.

In doing that BlueRev will ensure an efficient engagement of all actors, including local and regional authorities, primary biomass producers, SMEs, civil society organisations including NGOs, higher education organizations (e.g. universities including blue bioeconomy graduate courses), community knowledge and marginalised groups via robust and transparent communication and awareness-raising campaigns (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - BlueRev Concept

3 Research Data Management in BlueRev

3.1 Objectives of the DMP

Accessibility of the data during the project lifetime and beyond, and long-term data preservation are the ultimate goals of an effective data management, which is therefore an essential aspect of each research project, and it must be thoroughly planned since the early stages of the project. This deliverable aims at describing the overall data management process within BlueRev: how data will be collected, managed, stored and made available during the project lifetime, and how they will be stored and shared upon BlueRev completion. It is worth to point out that a proper data management plan can mitigate the risk of data loss or other threats that could render the data illegible or unusable.

Good data management is not a goal in itself, but rather is the key conduit essential for knowledge discovery and innovation, as it stimulates data and knowledge integration and reuse by the community after the data publication process¹. Given this, all data collected and generated during the BlueRev project will be managed following the FAIR principles to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

The management of the data produced during the project will aim to ensure open access taking also into consideration the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” principle, to ensure the adoption of suitable measures to preserve project results that can be further commercially exploited in the future (e.g. through patenting). Thus, the project will seek a balance between openness and protection of information, commercialization and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, security etc. In case project partners need to keep specific parts of their research data closed, the choice will be explicitly justified in the DMP.

3.2 The overall structure of the Data Management in BlueRev

This deliverable firstly describes the Data Collection within BlueRev, presented in Section 4. This section describes the methods of data collection for each Work Package (WP), as indicated by the Work Package Leaders. For each WP, the following items are checked and described, as far as applicable: type of data, aim of the data, formats, origin of the data and estimated size. The Data Collection section is essential to give a brief description of the data, including any existing data or third-party sources that will be used, providing information about its content, type and coverage.

The Section 5 will then describe where and how the data generated by the project activities will be stored. Information about the IT infrastructure used will be also provided.

¹ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

The Section 6 will detail how data will be documented to ensure that new members of the BlueRev team and/or any possible (secondary) users are able to understand and reuse the data. Additional information will be provided about the metadata used to provide indications about the identification and access to the data.

The Section 7 will mainly describe the level of data confidentiality and the responsibility of the individual organizations, within BlueRev, involved in the data collection process while the Section 8 will describe how the data will be shared and where they will be deposited.

Preserving all the material produced by the project will be a challenge. The Section 9 will therefore explain the general rules adopted by the project in order to preserve the main part of data generated.

Finally, Section 10 will detail the procedures to ensure the privacy of Participants to BlueRev activities.

3.3 Data management during BlueRev lifetime

The DMP will be updated at the end of the first reporting period (M18, February 2024). APRE will be responsible for coordinating the data management with the active support of WP Leaders and Task Leaders. The content of the data management plan will be reanalyzed and enriched in the update of the deliverable according to the project implementation progresses.

3.4 Long term data management

To be useful, findable and reusable over the long-term, data will be stored on ZENODO² that will automatically assign a persistent identifier, namely a DOI, to datasets to allow easy citation and discoverability. By archiving on ZENODO, the long-term preservation will be guaranteed, avoiding the risk of data loss.

² <https://zenodo.org/>

4 Data collection

4.1 Data information

During the BlueRev project, various types of data will be collected. This section describes the methods of data collection for each WP as indicated by the WP Leaders. For each WP, the following items are checked and described, as far as applicable.

Type of Data

In research projects, usually different types of data may be collected and documented. Since BlueRev is a Coordination and Support Action, no research data will be collected. However, the following categories of data will be collected in the project:

- **Technical Data:** recorded information related to technical/scientific activities (e.g. analysis of existing practices, development of new solutions, etc.). The collection may require surveys, interviews, instruments to record, transformation of existing datasets to create new data, etc.
- **Stakeholders Data:** such as Contact Details or any other (personal) data of BlueRev stakeholders. The collection may involve registration forms to event, newsletter subscription, website login, etc. The handling of those data will take into account GDPR.

It is worth to point out that administrative/financial data is not included in the technical data definition, and in BlueRev project it will be considered other data. Moreover, the identified categories can occasionally overlap, and data can belong to more than one category depending on the specificities of the data itself.

Aim of the data and the process of data collection

For each WP a short description of the aim of the data produced linked to the objectives of the Work Package is provided, together with a short description of the process of the data collection that will be applied.

Format of the data and estimated size

Research data come in various formats: text, numeric, multimedia, models, software languages, discipline and instrument specific, etc. For each WP, it will be described the format of the data produced, with the ultimate goal to facilitate the accessibility and interoperability of the data, giving preferences to open and standard formats. In this deliverable, a first estimation of the size of the data collected in each WP will also be provided. This information will be updated in the next version of BlueRev DMP according to the actual size of data collected.

4.2 Organization of data collected

The data collected within BlueRev will be organized taking into consideration the following aspects, as far as applicable.

Version Control

To overcome the challenge of managing and tracking research materials during the course of research, especially in collaborative projects, data will be organized to keep track of different versions of the datasets, through the application of a version control system. A version control system (or revision control system) is a system that tracks incremental versions (or revisions) of files and, in some cases, directories over time. Improving the ability to consistently track and retrieve each version of a file can lead to more efficient collaboration and increased accuracy of research results. Through the version control system, the risk of losing information after modifications is minimized.

Versioning is important for long term-research data management where metadata and/or files are updated over time.

Naming conventions used

With the overall aim to make the data accessible (and ultimately foster reproducible research), BlueRev datasets will be carefully named by choosing file names that are informative and useful for both humans and machines. Name should be meaningful so to make easier for others to understand what the file contains and how it should be used. Following, there are some suggestions about the naming conventions within BlueRev:

Choose machine readable names

Use deliberate delimits. Common approach is using “_” and “-” to delimit units of metadata in the file names. A general rule could be to use “-” to separate words you want to glob together and “_” to separate different information within a file name. Don't use spaces, punctuation, capital letters or special characters (Using \$, @, %, #, &, *, (,), !, etc. may have meanings in programming languages).

Choose human readable names

Choose names that explain the content. The more meaningful the name, the more useful it is for human users. The more metadata you store in the name, the less you need to explain elsewhere. Choose short names.

4.3 Data collected for each BlueRev Work Package

4.3.1 Work Package 1

Pre-Existing Data

Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement

Source of Pre-Existing data

Project proposal preparation

Conditions for use of pre-existing data

Data is available for internal use within BlueRev; no specific conditions applicable.

Type of data collected

- Technical data
- Stakeholders data
- Other

Aim of this data

This WP aims at ensuring: i) effective consortium coordination and project management according to the description of action; including the relevant administrative and financial procedures, communication within the consortium and with EC as well project meetings organization; ii) appropriate data management and personal data protection in line with EU rules.

Process of data collection

The data collected is related to financial aspects of the projects (i.e. costs declarations of the consortium partners) and the internal consortium meetings, and it comprises meeting minutes, presentations and recordings. Additional data could be generated through internal survey to collect feedback regarding specific issues related to project management.

Format of data collected

- ✓ .DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS /.XLSX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .CSV
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

Estimated size of data

15GB

4.3.2 Work Package 2

Pre-Existing Data

Grant Agreement

Source of Pre-Existing data

N/A

Conditions for use of pre-existing data

N/A

Type of data collected

- Technical data
- Stakeholders data
- Other

Aim of this data

WP2 aims at support the aggregation of different actors (local and regional authorities, primary biomass producers, SMEs, civil society organisations, etc.) through a stakeholders board and through a dedicated support tool for stakeholders to improve stakeholders' awareness and communication among them about the opportunities in the blue bioeconomy sector.

Process of data collection

The data collected will be related to stakeholders engagement activities. A list of stakeholders engaged by the project (Stakeholders Board) was developed and stored on the BlueRev sharepoint for internal use (see BlueRev D2.1 Stakeholders' board structure, communication tools and rules). Each partner will contribute to the list of stakeholders. Data related to stakeholders engagement activities (T2.2) will be related to events organized within the project. For each event, a list of participants and reference documents (i.e. presentations, event report) will be compiled and shared with the consortium.

Format of data collected

- ✓ .DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS / .XLSX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .CSV
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

Estimated size of data

5GB

4.3.3 Work Package 3

Pre-Existing Data

Literature study/review and open data

Source of Pre-Existing data

Open material

Conditions for use of pre-existing data

Each material that will be collected will be checked for permission to use and will be credited.

Type of data collected

- Technical data
- Stakeholders data
- Other

Aim of this data

WP3 aims at increasing knowledge about the effects of the current regional governance structures on the policy objectives at different scales for the targeted areas. This will be achieved through specific data collection on new business, governance models, sustainability assessments and models for social innovations. The data will also serve for building BlueRev web-based platform to facilitate cross-sector collaborations among stakeholders in the value chains of the bio-based economy contributing to the creation of a knowledge centre to i) share relevant information, to ii) make stakeholders aware about the possibilities offered by the uptake of the bioeconomy, ii) enhance cooperation opportunities, iii) train stakeholders, iv) allow collaboration and documents exchange among stakeholders

Process of data collection

The types of data collected include qualitative and quantitative data covering stakeholders' perceived limitations, barriers, opportunities and promoting circumstances related to revitalizing European coastal communities with innovative bio-based business, governance models and social innovations focused on the blue bio-based sector. The data set covers the important elements of the case study of interest (i.e. pilot regions). Surveys and business level data will be used to gather the necessary information. In order to limit the possibility to identify the respondents, raw data will be analysed on aggregated level.

Data collected for the sustainability assessment (using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)) of the different pilot regions will be of technical nature and include quantitative data detailing the production processes at the different localities.

The data will be collected at the case study locations/countries either digitally or in person, and data origins could be :

- Interviews with groups and individual participants in the pilot regions at each site
- Feedback Input from participants at stakeholder workshops
- Survey responses
- Market survey
- Literature study/review and open data (re-use of existing data)

Data containing sensitive information e.g. related to finance or production, or other business information will be confidential while aggregated results that do not contain personal information will be open and accessible for the duration of the project website's life. Data that contains any personal information must be irreversibly anonymised before being made public, if such publication should be deemed to be in the interest of the project. If such data cannot be irreversibly anonymised, it will remain confidential within the consortium.

Technical data detailing the production processes at the production sites in the pilot regions will be confidential and only managed by the Beneficiary leading the activity (see Section 10). Unless further agreed upon with the respective production sites this data will remain confidential even after the project has ended.

RISE will follow internal project documentation and quality assurance processes throughout the project.

Format of data collected

- ✓ .DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS / .XLSX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .CSV
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

Estimated size of data

2GB

4.3.4 Work Package 4

Pre-Existing Data

Data collected in WP3

Source of Pre-Existing data

WP3

Conditions for use of pre-existing data

Grant Agreement

Type of data collected

- Technical data
- Stakeholders data
- Other

Aim of this data

The data collected in this WP aims at developing new solutions for governance, business models and social innovations based on the information collected and analysed in the BlueRev WP3.

Process of data collection

Data collected in this WP will be mainly related to stakeholders' participation in BlueRev engagement activities to co-create new solutions. The data will be collected at the case study locations/countries either digitally or in person, through interviews, surveys, registration forms, etc. The data will be anonymized upon collection to remove any personal identifiers, before being made public. If such data cannot be irreversibly anonymised, it will remain confidential within the consortium.

Format of data collected

- ✓ DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS / .XLSX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .CSV
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

Estimated size of data

5GB

4.3.5 Work Package 5

Pre-Existing Data

Data collected in WP3-WP4

Source of Pre-Existing data

WP3-WP4

Conditions for use of pre-existing data

Grant Agreement

Type of data collected

- Technical data
- Stakeholders data
- Other

Aim of this data

Data collected in this WP aims at supporting pilot regions with the new solutions developed in WP4.

Process of data collection

Data collected in this WP will be mainly related to stakeholders' participation in BlueRev engagement activities to test the new solutions developed in WP4. The data will be collected at the case study locations/countries either digitally or in person, through interviews, surveys, registration forms, etc. If such data cannot be irreversibly anonymised, it will remain confidential within the consortium (see Section 10). Moreover, data collected in this WP will be related to training sessions, mainly online. During the training programme implementation data collected and generated, will include:

- List of participants
- Slides of the presentations
- Video Recording

In the development of the guidelines, data about existing good practices will be collected. The data will be mainly text and stored in a spreadsheet.

Format of data collected

- ✓ DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS / .XLSX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .CSV
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

Estimated size of data

10GB

4.3.6 Work Package 6

Pre-Existing Data

N/A

Source of Pre-Existing data

N/A

Conditions for use of pre-existing data

N/A

Type of data collected

- Technical data
- Stakeholders data
- Other

Aim of this data

WP6 aims at establishing the project's identity and visibility in Europe. It will develop the necessary support to the promotion of project outcomes and will sustain the expected achievements of the project. It structures all dissemination, communication and exploitation processes, both within the project and most importantly, towards the BlueRev target groups.

Process of data collection

The main part of data collected in this WP is related to statistical data about the communication and dissemination activities. Statistical data about communication and dissemination activities will be generated by the main communication channels, i.e. website, social media accounts (see D6.1 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including communication activities). Other data collected will be personal data, i.e. subscribers to the project's newsletter, list of participants to outreach events, etc. The dataset with contact information from subscribers to the project mailing list/newsletter will include contact information such as name and email. The collected data is necessary for distributing the project's updates. The dataset of stakeholders registered to the support tool on the website may contain personal information, including name, short profile/short bio, affiliation, social media channels and email of the contact person.

Moreover, the project website, apart from the data gathering through forms, will be using as well Google Analytics 4 (GA4) for the measuring of its performance (number of visitors, countries, demographics etc). Thus, a specific Privacy Policy and Cookies Policy have been developed in order to convey in a transparent way to the users what kind of data is collected. The referred policies are included as annex in the end of this document and also published in the website of the project.

Format of data collected

- ✓ DOC /.DOCX
- ✓ .XLS / .XLSX
- ✓ .PPT / .PPTX
- ✓ .CSV
- ✓ .PDF
- ✓ Photo Format (e.g., .JPEG, .PNG)
- ✓ Video Format (e.g., .MKV, .MP4, .AVI)

Estimated size of data

2GB

5 Data storage and backup

BlueRev involves the collaboration between 8 beneficiaries and a moderate amount of data will be generated in various activities. To manage such quantities of data, with the aim to follow the FAIR principles and to stimulate the collaboration among partners, a few data storage tools have been selected. The selection was made having in mind the purposes and the end-users of the data stored, divided in tools appropriate for internal use and daily project activities, and tools for guaranteeing the long-term storage of BlueRev data.

List of storage tools NOT appropriate for long-term storing of data generated by BlueRev project but used to carry out daily project activities:

- Microsoft SharePoint: is a file hosting service and synchronization service operated by Microsoft as part of its web version of Office. It is a private space, created for the project activities (as detailed in BlueRev D1.1 Project Management Plan), used by all beneficiaries to share working files and store temporary master copy of raw data that should be available for use by other beneficiaries for data processing.
- Local drives, company cloud storage and external portable storage devices: these are storage facilities that do not fall under surveillance of this data management plan. These are very common and convenient for individual short-term storage of data.

List of storage tools appropriate for long-term storing of data and to guarantee the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data generated by BlueRev:

- Zenodo: A BlueRev Zenodo community has been created. BlueRev datasets will be stored there. Data files are versioned. The uploaded data is archived as a Submission Information Package. Derivatives of data files are generated, but original content is never modified. All data files are stored in CERN Data Centres, primarily Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, which is backed up to tape on a nightly basis. All data files are stored along with a MD5 checksum of the file content. Files are regularly checked against their checksums to assure that file content remains constant. Each beneficiary has the possibility to upload the data produced by their project activities in the community and a moderator will validate it. Each data-set will have a readme file.

Link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/BlueRev/?page=1&size=20>

6 Data documentation

All data are documented to help interested users to clearly understand and reuse them. For this reason, descriptive and substantive (i.e. how the data should be read or interpreted) metadata will be elaborated and described in a readme.txt file complementing each dataset (see Table 6-1).

Table 6-1 - Metadata included in the readme file of BlueRev data

Creator*	Main researchers involved in producing the data.
Title*	Name or title by which the dataset is known.
Contributor	Institution where the data was created or collected. A person or organization responsible for making contributions to the dataset.
Publisher	A holder of the data (including archives appropriate) or institution which submitted the work. Any others may be listed as contributors.
Publication year*	The year when the data was or will be made publicly available.
Date created*	Date the resource itself was put together; this could be a date range or a single date.
Description*	Concise description of the contents of the dataset. Describe the research objective, type of research, method of data collection and type of data.
Subject	Subject, keyword, or key phrase describing the resource.
Temporal coverage	Indicate the dates to which the data refer. Enter the year or beginning and ending dates.
Spatial coverage	Describe the geographic area to which the data refer (e.g. municipality, town/city, region, country). The geographic coordinates of the area may be included, if desired.
Identifier	Zenodo automatically assigns a DOI to a dataset once the entire deposit procedure has been completed. In some cases, a dataset may be known by one or more other (persistent) identifiers.
Language*	The primary language of the resource.
Link to publication	Include the web addresses or DOIs for any publication, important internal reports or other datasets that are related to your dataset.

File naming & Identifiers

In BlueRev project, an identifier is used as a reference number or name for a data object. The identifier is a key part of our documentation and metadata. Table 6-2 shows the codes that can be used for making identifiers.

Table 6-2 - Examples of files identification

Description	Deliverables	Meetings	Conferences/Events
First Letters	BlueRev	BlueRev	BlueRev
Underscore	_	_	_
Next letters	Deliverable number (Dx.y) [x=WP number, y=deliverable number]	Type of document (i.e. Agenda, Minutes, Presentation). In case of presentations, mention WP number as well.	Event title
Underscore	_	_	_
Next letters	Short explanatory title for the document	Location and date of the meeting separated by underscore	Location and date of the meeting separated by underscore
Underscore	_	_	_
Next letters		Short name of organisation and initials of presenter	Short name of organisation and initials of presenter
Underscore	_	_	_
Last letters	"v" and number of revision of this specific report [v0.1=draft version, v1.0=final version]	"v" and number of revision of this specific report [v0.1=draft version, v1.0=final version]	"v" and number of revision of this specific report [v0.1=draft version, v1.0=final version]

7 Data access

The main part of raw and processed data generated by the project will be accessible to all consortium partners. It will be stored in BlueRev SharePoint site. Only members of consortium, after validation from the group administrator (i.e. APRE), can access this space. The public data will be accessible by Zenodo.

The data containing personal data and the data gathered through questionnaires, interviews, focus groups, workshops and through other data gathering methods used during the project will be anonymised by default; for the purposes of the project's activities (specifically stakeholders engagement related activities, as a crucial element of the project), with prior expressed consent to share personal data, they will be used and will not be made accessible for any third party. Raw data like interview protocols and audio files is shared within the consortium partners and with external open repositories only upon agreement of the participants (agreement via informed consent) and in anonymised form. The stored data does not contain the names or addresses of participants and is edited for full anonymity before being processed (e.g. in project reports). Confidential data and data collected for internal purposes is stored in the secure facilities of the organization responsible for collecting the data and is retained for two years after the end of project. If requested and agreed by the participants, data can be shared with other consortium members through the online repository (internal one, see Section 5 Data storage and backup).

In case of data that cannot be accessible to public, it will be stored in Zenodo (to preserve it) but only the metadata will be public (in CC 0).

Details concerning the ownership, transfer and dissemination of projects results are defined in section 8 of the BlueRev Consortium Agreement and shall be followed accordingly. The relevant rules of the Grant Agreement, in specific Article 13, Article 15, Article 16 and Annex 5, are also relevant and apply accordingly.

8 Data sharing and reuse

BlueRev beneficiaries will be the main users of data produced in the project. In BlueRev, all data may be classified into open, sensitive and closed. Access depends on the classification of the data.

- Open data must be acknowledged by citing the data set. Permission from the researcher is not required.
- Sensitive (or confidential/restricted data) may be made available by the researcher after any identifying information has been removed. Then, they can be used and cited. Permission from the researcher could be sought.
- Closed data are not available for sharing.

In any case, the main part of BlueRev data will have the CC-BY license.

Details concerning the ownership, transfer and dissemination of projects results are defined in section 8 of the BlueRev Consortium Agreement and shall be followed accordingly. The relevant rules of the Grant Agreement, in specific Article 13, Article 15, Article 16 and Annex 5, are also relevant and apply accordingly.

9 Data preservation and archiving

All relevant obtained data will be preserved and archived in ZENODO. All data and items on ZENODO will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.

10 Privacy of participants

Since BlueRev activities involve the processing of personal data, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (GDPR) and other relevant EU-level³ and relevant national legal acts shall be complied with and respected by the consortium as a whole, as well as by each project Beneficiary which will deal with personal data processing in the context of project implementation.

According to Art. 4(1) of GDPR, **personal data** ‘means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person’. Examples of personal data protection typically cover: names and surname, home and email address, an identification card number, location data and IP address or a cookie ID. **Processing of personal data** is defined in Art. 4(2) of the Regulation and means ‘any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organization, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction’.

In its Art. 5, the GDPR provides for the **principles of personal data processing**, stating that personal data must be:

- ‘processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject (‘lawfulness, fairness and transparency’);
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes (...) (‘purpose limitation’);
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed (‘data minimization’);
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the

³ Regulation (EC) N° 45/2001 of the European Parliament and the Council of 18 December 2000 in the protection of individuals regarding the processing of personal data by the Community institutions and bodies and on the free movement of such data, Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purpose of prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences, Directive 2000/31/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2000 on certain legal aspects of information society services, in particular electronic commerce in the Internal Market, Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2002 concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector.

- purposes for which they are processed, are erased or rectified without delay ('accuracy');
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed (...) ('storage limitation');
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorized or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organizational measures ('integrity and confidentiality').

In order to fulfill to the GDPR requirements, there is a set of indications that each BlueRev Beneficiary dealing with data processing will respect during the project implementation:

1) Consent

Participation of third parties in the BlueRev project is voluntary and individual participants agree to participate in project activities (both online and physical) based on the invitation issued. The consent should be given by an individual (data subject) in a free, specific, informed and unambiguous manner, by way of a request presented in clear and plain language. Moreover, the consent should be given by an affirmative act, such as checking a box online or signing a form. Therefore, along with an invitation, participants receive an informed consent (see Appendix 1 and Appendix 2) and agree to participate, before the commencement of any project activity requiring their involvement, in compliance with GDPR.

2) Providing transparent information

Individuals must be clearly informed on who is processing their personal data as well as what data will be processed, why and how. In addition to the above information, individuals should be also informed about who will receive the data, how long the data will be stored, the individual's data protection rights (i.e. right to access, correction, erasure, restriction, objection, portability, etc.), whether there is a statutory or contractual obligation to provide the data and how consent can be withdrawn.

3) Ensuring the right to access and right to data portability

Individuals must be ensured with the right to request access to their personal data, free of charge and in an accessible format. In addition, when the processing is based on consent or a contract, the individual can ask for their personal data to be returned or transmitted to another company (right to portability).

4) Ensuring the right to erasure (right to be forgotten)

An individual has the right to request the data controller to erase their personal data, such as when the data is no longer needed to fulfil the processing purpose. The data controller is not obliged to comply with such request if: the processing is necessary to respect one's freedom of expression and information, they must keep the personal data to comply with a legal obligation; there are other reasons of public interest to keep the

personal data, such as public health or scientific and historical research purposes; they need to keep the personal data to establish a legal claim.

5) Ensuring the right to correct and right to object

If an individual thinks that their personal data is incorrect, incomplete or inaccurate, they have the right to have it rectified or completed without undue delay

6) Obligation of data protection by design and by default

In order to minimize privacy risks and increase trust, a data controller must take all necessary steps (e.g. pseudonymization) to implement the data protection principles and protect the rights of individuals (data protection by design). In accordance with the obligation of data protection by default, the entity processing personal data should ensure that the most privacy friendly setting is the default setting.

7) Obligation to provide proper notification in the case of a data breach

In case a data breach occurs, and the breach poses a risk to individual rights and freedoms, the entity processing personal data should notify the relevant Data Protection Authority within 72 hours after becoming aware of the breach. If the data breach poses a high risk to those affected, the entity may also be required to inform all individuals affected by the data breach.

Appendix 1 – Informed consent for events participation

I hereby authorise Beneficiaries of the Horizon Europe BlueRev project (Grant Agreement No. 101060537) to collect, process and store information about my name, surname, affiliation and contact information (email) for up to five years after the project ends for the purpose of project implementation, specifically for recording information about my registration and participation in project meetings and events (workshops, webinars, etc.), in paper and digital form.

I also authorise Beneficiaries of the Horizon Europe BlueRev project to take pictures of me and to record my image in the form of a video in each location where project meetings or project activities take place, including online events (subject to the project's confidentiality and security rules set out in the Grant Agreement), during the whole duration of the project to be used for the reporting and promotional purposes of the project and affiliated activities. With respect to this, these pictures and videos can be recorded, stored, processed, reproduced, exhibited and publicly published by any member of the BlueRev consortium as well as any third party contracted to produce the promotional material of the project, using any kind of media (including paper, computer, audio-visual, etc.), up to five years after the project ends.

The information provided by me during the project event (e.g. professional opinions) can only be used for research purposes related to the project implementation.

The information provided by me as well as my image will not be transferred to any third party nor processed in a manner inconsistent with the purposes for which they have been initially collected, without prejudice to any applicable legal provision of any kind.

I acknowledge that I received all the required information about the data processing. I confirm that I am aware of my right to access any personal data related to me, the right to modify or rectify these data, cancel as well as object to the use of data and to ask for restriction of processing these data. I can also withdraw my consent for the future use at any time without any justification.

To exercise the above-mentioned rights, please send a written request to info@BlueRevproject.eu.

FULL NAME	
EMAIL	
ORGANISATION	
COUNTRY	
I REPRESENT	<input type="checkbox"/> Research communities <input type="checkbox"/> Industry, business partners <input type="checkbox"/> Innovators <input type="checkbox"/> Investors <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.) <input type="checkbox"/> EU Institutions <input type="checkbox"/> National authorities <input type="checkbox"/> Regional authorities <input type="checkbox"/> Local authorities <input type="checkbox"/> Civil society <input type="checkbox"/> Citizens <input type="checkbox"/> Specific end user communities <input type="checkbox"/> Other
<p>By signing this document, I confirm that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I have read the above-mentioned information • I am clearly informed about my data protection rights • I voluntarily agree to participate in the event • I am at least 18 years of age <p>Moreover,</p> <input type="checkbox"/> I agree to the processing of my personal data for the purpose of event participation <input type="checkbox"/> I agree to the use of my image (video and photos) for BlueRev reporting and promotional purposes	
DATE	SIGNATURE

Appendix 2 – Informed consent for interviews and surveys

PARTICIPATION

Your participation in this interview is voluntary. You may refuse to take part without providing a justification. Please be aware that if you do decide to participate, you may also stop participating at any time without penalty. You have the right to access your data at any time, and the right to modify, rectify, withdraw, or restrict processing of your data until such time the data have been anonymised or analysed. The data provided by you will not be transferred to any third party nor processed in a manner inconsistent with the purposes for which they have been initially collected, without prejudice to any applicable legal provision of any kind.

BENEFITS

You will receive no direct benefits from participating. However, your responses will help us to complete and improve the BlueRev project.

RISKS

There are no foreseeable risks involved in participating in this [survey/interview]. By answering the questions, you grant permission for the data generated from this questionnaire to be used ONLY for research purposes related to the project implementation and promotion. The results may be disseminated in scientific publications, public reports, blog posts, and other public media wherein anonymity will be guaranteed, unless you have consented to be quoted. Participants' statements may be used in reports as quotes, but in such a way that anonymity is ensured when no explicit consent for citation was given.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your answers and data will be stored in a password-protected electronic format and your responses will remain anonymous. No one outside the BlueRev consortium will be able to identify you or your answers, and no one will know you participated in the study.

DATA STORAGE

The collected data will be kept for 5 years after the end of the project and will then be destroyed.

CONTACT

If you have questions about the project or the data protection procedures and/or would like to exercise your data protection rights, you may contact our project coordinator via email at info@BlueRevproject.eu.

If you do not agree, you are unfortunately not able to participate in this interview.

FULL NAME	
EMAIL	
ORGANISATION	
COUNTRY	
I REPRESENT	<input type="checkbox"/> communities <input type="checkbox"/> Industry, business partners <input type="checkbox"/> Innovators <input type="checkbox"/> Investors <input type="checkbox"/> International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.) <input type="checkbox"/> EU Institutions <input type="checkbox"/> National authorities <input type="checkbox"/> Regional authorities <input type="checkbox"/> Local authorities <input type="checkbox"/> Civil society <input type="checkbox"/> Citizens <input type="checkbox"/> Specific end user communities <input type="checkbox"/> Other
<p>By signing this document, I confirm that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I have read the above-mentioned information • I am clearly informed about my data protection rights • I voluntarily agree to participate in interview/survey • My anonymous answers can be used for research purposes • I am at least 18 years of age 	
DATE	SIGNATURE

Appendix 3 – Website Privacy Policy

This privacy policy governs the use of your personal data by BlueRev project – this project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101060537 – ; communicate with us via e-mail, telephone, fax, the contact form available on the website and our social medial channels; e.g. LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube (hereafter referred to as “Social Media Channels”); or interact with us at fairs and events.

NOTE: If you want information on how we process personal data via cookies on our Website, you are kindly referred to our [Cookies Policy](#).

Who is responsible for the processing of your personal data?

Your personal data are processed by Globaz, S.A, dissemination and communication partner of BlueRev project – this project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101060537. You can contact us via e-mail at info@BlueRevproject.eu

Globaz S.A reserves the right to modify, change or amend this Privacy Policy at its own discretion and from time to time. Such modifications, changes or amendments shall be communicated via the Website. In case of questions or comments with regard to the modifications, changes or amendments, you can inform us by sending an e-mail to info@BlueRevproject.eu

What categories of personal data do we process?

When you fill out the contact form on our Website, or contact us via e-mail, telephone, fax or Social Media Channels, we collect:

- The basic identity information you provide us with, such as name, e-mail address, postal address, telephone number, the company you work for, your function;
- The content of your communication and the technical details of the communication itself (with whom you correspond at our end, date and time, etc.);
- Your preferences regarding receiving our e-mail communications, such as newsletters, advertisements, etc;
- Electronic identification data, such as ip address;
- Publicly available information of your profile on social media channels and any other personal data you choose to provide to us.

Whenever you leave us your business card or interact with us at fairs and events at which we are present, we may collect:

- The basic identity information you provide us with, such as name, e-mail address, postal address, telephone number, the company you work for, your function (i.e. When such information is provided by you or shown on your business card);

- Your image.

For what purpose do we use your personal data?

Globaz, S.A processes your personal data to provide you in a personalized and efficient way with the information, products and/or services you request via the Website, e-mail, telephone, fax, Social Media Channels and fairs and events.

Globaz, S.A processes your personal data to communicate with you as a result of our contact at a trade fair and/or event or as a result of your approach via the Website, e-mail, telephone, fax or one of our Social Media Channels.

Globaz, S.A processes your personal data to perform statistical analyses so that we may improve our Website, our products and services or develop new products and services.

Globaz, S.A processes your personal data to comply with legal obligations or to comply with any reasonable request from competent law enforcement agents or representatives, judicial authorities, governmental agencies or bodies, including competent data protection authorities. Your personal data may be transferred upon BlueRev 's own initiative to the police or the judicial authorities as evidence or if there are justified suspicions of an unlawful act or crime committed by you through your registration with or use of the Website, our Social Media Channels or other communication with us.

Globaz, S.A may process your personal data for informing any third party in the context of a possible merger with, acquisition from/by or demerger by that third party, even if that third party is located outside the EU.

Globaz, S.A may process your personal data for the preservation of the legitimate interests of BlueRev project, its partners or a third party if and when your registration with, or use of, the Website, Social Media Channels or other communication channels can be considered (a) a violation of any applicable terms of use or the intellectual property rights or any other right of a third party, (b) a threat to the security or integrity of the Website, (c) a danger to the Website or any of BlueRev project's or its subcontractors' underlying systems due to viruses, Trojan horses, spyware, malware or any other form of malicious code, or (d) in any way hateful, obscene, discriminating, racist, slanderous, spiteful, hurtful or in some other way inappropriate or illegal.

Globaz, S.A processes your personal data mentioned under clauses 2.1, 2.2 above for marketing purposes, i.e. to provide you with targeted communications, promotions, offerings and other advertisements of BlueRev project and selected partners. BlueRev project will only send you communications, promotions, offerings, newsletters and other advertisements via e-mail or other person-to-person electronic communications channels if you have explicitly consented to receiving such communications, newsletters and other advertisements.

Why is our processing of your personal data legitimate?

For the processing of your personal data for the purpose outlined in clause 3.1, we ask for your consent.

The processing of your personal data for the purpose outlined in clause 3.4 is necessary to allow BlueRev project to comply with its legal obligations.

The processing of your personal data for the purposes outlined in clauses 3.2, 3.3, 3.6 and 3.7 is necessary for the purpose of the legitimate interests of BlueRev project, which are:

- Being able to appropriately respond to your requests for information and other requests;
- Communicate your personal data to our partners in the BlueRev project to provide you with adequate information;
- Allowing us to defend ourselves in legal proceedings;
- Continuous improvements to the Website, our Social Media Channels, products and services to ensure that you have the best experience possible;
- Keeping our Website, Social Media Channels, products and services safe from misuse and illegal activity;
- Safeguarding our commercial and business interests and needs in light of changing market conditions.
- Marketing and promotion of our products, services, brands an overall successful commercialization of our products and services.

For processing your personal data for the purposes outlined in in clause 3.1, Globaz, S.A as the responsible party asks for your consent. By consenting to our processing of your personal data for sending you communications, promotions, offerings, newsletters and other advertisements via e-mail or other person-to-person electronic communications channels, you agree that we are allowed to process your personal data for this purpose in the manner and under the conditions outlined in this Privacy Policy.

What are our quality assurances?

Globaz, S.A does its utmost to process only those personal data which are necessary to achieve the purposes listed under the purpose for processing.

Your personal data is processed only for as long as necessary for the purposes listed above or up until such time where you withdraw your consent for processing them. Globaz, S.A will de-identify your personal data when they are no longer necessary for the purposes outlined in the purpose for processing, unless there is:

- An overriding interest of BlueRev project or any other third party in keeping your personal data identifiable;
- A legal or regulatory obligation or a judicial or administrative order that prevents BlueRev project from de-identifying them.

Globaz, S.A will take the appropriate technical and organizational measures to keep your personal data safe from unauthorized access or theft as well as accidental loss, tampering or destruction. Access by personnel of Globaz, S.A or its third party processors will only be on a need-to-know basis and subject to strict confidentiality obligations. You understand, however, that safety and security are best efforts obligations only, which can never be guaranteed.

What are your rights?

You have the right to request access to all personal data processed by Globaz, S.A pertaining to you. Globaz, S.A reserves the right to charge an administrative fee for multiple subsequent requests for access that are clearly submitted for causing nuisance or harm to BlueRev project.

You have the right to ask that any personal data pertaining to you that are inaccurate, are corrected free of charge. If a request for correction is submitted, such request shall be accompanied of proof of the flawed nature of the data for which correction is asked.

You have the right to withdraw your earlier given consent under clause 4.4 for processing your personal data.

You have the right to request that personal data pertaining to you will be deleted if they are no longer required in light of the purposes which are outlined above or if you withdraw your consent for processing them. However, you need to keep in mind that a request for deletion will be evaluated by Globaz, S.A against:

- Overriding interests of BlueRev project or any other third party;
- Legal or regulatory obligations or administrative or judicial orders which may contradict such deletion.

Instead of deletion you can also ask that Globaz, S.A limits the processing of your personal data if and when (a) you contest the accuracy of that data, (b) the processing is illegitimate or (c) the data are no longer needed for the purposes which are outlined above, but you need them to defend yourself in judicial proceedings.

You have the right to oppose the processing of personal data if you are able to prove that there are serious and justified reasons connected with his particular circumstances that warrant such opposition. However, if the intended processing qualifies as direct marketing, you have the right to oppose such processing free of charge and without justification.

You have the right to receive from us in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format all personal data you have provided to us.

If you wish to submit a request to exercise one or more of the rights listed above, you can send an e-mail to info@BlueRevproject.eu for all data subject rights matters. An e-mail requesting to exercise a right shall not be construed as consent with the processing of your personal data beyond what is required for handling your request.

Such request should clearly state and specify which right you wish to exercise and the reasons for it if such is required. It should also be dated and signed, and accompanied by a digitally scanned copy of your valid identity card proving your identity. BlueRev project will promptly inform you of having received this request. If the request proves valid, BlueRev project shall notify it as soon as reasonably possible and at the latest thirty (30) days after having received the request. If you have any complaint regarding the processing of your personal data by Globaz, S.A, you may always contact BlueRev project via the e-mail address mentioned in the first paragraph of this clause. If you remain unsatisfied with BlueRev project's response, you are free to file a complaint with the competent data protection authority, i.e. the data protection authority of the country where you reside or the Portuguese data protection authority (Comissão Nacional de Proteção de Dados). For more information, visit <https://www.cnpd.pt/index.asp>.

Appendix 4 – Website Cookies Policy

What are Cookies?

“Cookies” are small text files that are stored on your computer through the Internet browser, only retaining information related to your preferences and therefore not including your personal data.

What are Cookies for?

Cookies help determine the usefulness, interest and number of uses of your websites, allowing for faster and more efficient browsing, eliminating the need to repeatedly enter the same information.

What type of Cookies do we use?

There are two groups of cookies that can be used:

- **Permanent Cookies:** These are cookies that are stored in the browser in your access equipment (PC, mobile and tablet) and are used whenever you visit one of our websites more than once. They are generally used to direct the browsing to the user’s interests, allowing us to provide a more personalised service.
- **Session Cookies:** These are temporary cookies that remain in your browser’s cookie file until you leave the website. The information obtained by these cookies serves to analyse patterns of web traffic, allowing us to identify problems and provide a better browsing experience.

For what purposes do we use Cookies?

Strictly necessary Cookies: They allow you to browse the website and use its applications as well as to access secure areas of the website. Without these cookies, the services you have requested cannot be provided.

Functional Cookies: They store user preferences for site usage so that you do not need to reconfigure the site each time you visit it.

Advertising Cookies: They direct advertising according to the interests of each user so as to direct advertising campaigns, taking into account the tastes of users, and they also limit the number of times you see the ad, helping to measure the effectiveness of advertising and the success of the website organisation.

How can you manage Cookies?

All browsers allow users to accept, reject or delete cookies, in particular by selecting the appropriate settings in their browser. You can set cookies in the “options” or “preferences” menu of your browser. Note, however, that by disabling cookies you can prevent certain web services from functioning properly, partially or totally affecting

browsing of the website. Users can disable the use of cookies on this web page at any time by modifying browser settings, for example:

- Google Chrome
- Internet Explorer
- Mozilla Firefox
- Apple Safari

What happens when Cookies are disabled?

Certain functions and services may stop working or behave unexpectedly, such as identifying the user on certain pages or receiving information that takes into account the location of the user, among others. If you disable the cookies on this web page, you may not have access to certain areas or the quality of your browsing experience may be considerably lower

The Cookies used on this web page

Bellow follows a summary of the cookies used on the BlueRev page:

First Party Cookies

Provider	Cookies	Duration	Type	Purpose
www.BlueRevproject.eu/	eucookie-complete	One year	Permanent	Identify whether the user has already accepted the cookie policy.

Third Party Cookies

Provider	Cookies	Duration	Type	Purpose
Google	PREF, HSID, SAPISID, SID, 1P_JAR, SIDCC, NID, SSID, OGPC, CONSENT, 1P_JAR,	Two years	Permanent	When you create a Google Account or log in, the PREF, NID, HSID, APISID, SID, SSID, SAPISID, GAPS, LSID, BEAT and ULS cookies are stored on your computer to remain connected to your Google Account when you use the service again. While you are authenticated and use plugins from other websites,

	S_adsense 3-ui			such as ours, Google uses these cookies to enhance your user experience. Some of the cookies are also used to enhance your browsing experience, e.g. when using Google maps
--	-------------------	--	--	---

Additional guarantees and withdrawal of acceptance

BlueRev Project will not be held liable for the content and veracity of the privacy policies of third party components that may be included in this web page. As an additional guarantee, the recording of cookies on this website may be subject to users accepting the cookies during their visit to the web page and the installation or update of the browser used. This acceptance may be revoked at any time in the content and privacy settings, as defined above in point 5 of this policy, or by using the link at the bottom of this page.

Cookie policy update

BlueRev Project may change this cookie policy in accordance with legal or regulatory requirements or adapt this policy to new instructions provided by law. Whenever significant changes are made to this cookie policy, users of the web page will be notified.

More information on Cookies

More information about cookies can be found on this link: www.allaboutcookies.org

Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

Consortium

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

www.blurevproject.eu info@blurevproject.eu

[f](#) [in](#) [t](#) [@](#) [@BlueRevEU](#)

